

Kidnapping and National Security in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined Kidnapping and National Security in Nigeria. The paper argued that there are some objective conditions which have led to kidnapping, and unless such objective conditions are curbed or totally eliminated, kidnapping would continue to threaten national security in Nigeria. The frustration-Aggression theory was used as analytical construct. One of the major assumptions of the theory is that when people are unable to achieve their expected goals or live a fulfilled life, they become frustrated and aggressive. Secondary sources of data were relied on in this paper. One of the findings in this paper is that due to harsh economic realities like unemployment and poverty, most people in Nigeria have resorted to kidnapping as a means of eking out a living and enhancing their social status. The paper recommended, among others, that Nigerian government should create economic activities which can engage its citizens for a fruitful livelihood devoid of criminalities like kidnapping in Nigeria.

Key Words: Kidnapping, National Security, Frustration; Aggression.

INTRODUCTION

It is the desire of man to survive in every society he finds himself. Man is the architect of development and should be beneficiary of the end product of development. There should be a guarantee of the sources of livelihood for man, especially when viewed from the gregarious nature of man who live in a community with his fellow man. The unlimited wants of man in the face of scarce resources logically calls for prudent management and fair distribution of scarce resources in a community or state. The state as part of its basic functions, should as a matter of necessity, not only ensure prudent management but also fair and equitable distribution of the, scarce resources. This would go a long way to ensure peaceful, just and egalitarian society. But when the scarce resources of a state are not prudently managed, and unfairly distributed, partly as a result of the primitive accumulation mentality of the actors of the state, the sources of livelihood of the people are undermined, and the people can do anything humanly possible to survive. Consequently, kidnapping has become a precipitate of such

faulty distributive mechanism that places more wealth in the hands few individuals, while the majority of the people are wallowing in seemingly abysmal poverty.

Kidnaping has manifested itself as a social problem affecting virtually every member of the Nigerian society in one way or the other, and has great devastating effects. The proliferation of kidnapping has brought along with it the problem of insecurity of lives and property, and a general fall in the number of economic activities as a result of the fear of the unknown. Monday (2015) buttressed the fact that the issues of kidnapping have taken an alarming dimension, thereby, creating anxiety among the people in Nigeria. It is disheartening that despite the stringent laws promulgated (ranging from 10 years imprisonment to life imprisonment in some states), kidnapping seems to triumph unabated. Kidnapping industries in Nigeria now thrive very well amidst concerted efforts by law enforcement agents to curb the menace and its unpalatable effects.

The business is very lucrative in Nigeria where the perpetrators and the sponsors receive huge sums of money from their victims, sometimes the victims of kidnapping are murdered, raped, drugged, battered, and even butchered in the act whenever the amount of money demanded from them are not met in time or not redeemed. Moreso, the victims are often times kept in deplorable places, exposed to adverse harsh weather conditions. They (victims) are maltreated, ill-fed, emotionally and psychologically tortured. Access to medication becomes a serious challenge in the process. The kidnappers are careful in the acts to make sure they evade arrest, get their ransom, and enjoy their ill-gotten money unnoticed.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK – FRUSTRATION – AGGRESSION

The Frustration-Aggression (F-A_ theory simply states that frustration leads to aggressive behaviour. In their views (Dollard et al, (1939) as cited in Dennen (2005), averred that “aggression is always a consequence of frustration”. The frustration-aggression theory was propagated in 1939 by John Dollard, Leonard Dooh, Nical Miller, O. H. Mowrer and Bobert Sears who were associates at the Yale University. Frustration sets in as encumbrances which impede goal attainment (Wonah, 2018). The inability to achieve a goal involves sense of frustration and the consequence is aggression. Every man is driven by the innate desire to survive and live a decent and fulfilled life (Wonah, 2018). But when the sources of survival are threatened or frustrated, man does anything humanly possible to survive.

Thus, frustration can lead to aggressive behaviour like violence, insurgency, electoral violence, conflict, militancy, agitation for secession, perpetration of social vices such as armed robbery, kidnapping, prostitution and indeed general insecurity. From the foregoing, the paper considered the objective conditions that gave rise to kidnapping in Nigeria. The primitive accumulation mentality with the concomitant faulty distributive mechanism have led to harsh economic conditions which threaten sources of livelihood of the people, and frustrate their efforts in achieving their goals in life. Aggressive behaviour in the form of kidnapping, therefore becomes a consequence for most people as a result of frustration.

CONCEPTUALISING KIDNAPPING

The term kidnapping has generated many controversies in definition and conceptualization. Aderibigbe (2014) defines kidnapping as the taking away of a person against the person's will, usually for ransom or in furtherance of another crime. The furtherance of other crimes could be for organ harvesting, rituals, or political purposes amongst others. Asuquo (2009) however, argued that kidnapping does not have any straight definition as it varies from state to state and jurisdiction to jurisdiction. Onyejebu (2018) submits that it is the "forceful seizure, taking away, and unlawful detention of a person against his/her will". In the opinion of Seigel (2002) it is a grievous crime and must be dealt with utmost seriousness. Moreover, Thomas and Nta (2009) posited that kidnapping is a "robbery of the highest rank". They buttressed that "it is an organized and systematic robbery which is not deadly as armed robbery, but more profitable than the former" Nwaorah (2009) submits that kidnapping is an act of an aggrieved man who wants to take a person of value hostage, to be rescued by loved ones.

Ogabido (2009) summarizes kidnapping to mean "to abduct, capture, carry off, remove or steal away a person" Bello and Jamilu (2017) added that it is usually motivated by political demand or financial gain. They further stated that political and traditional crimes can resort to the act of kidnapping to gain financial resources or have their request met. Based on the views above, one can submit that all the definitions are united in one factor, which is that; Kidnapping is a criminal act which involves the use of force and also violates the sole rights of the victims. However, all the authors believe that it is carried out to obtain ransom. However, the study borrows the submission of Nnam (2014) who defines Kidnapping as an "Unlawful and coercive taking away of a person or group of persons without their

volition to an undisclosed hostile environment often to demand and obtain a ransom, or to settle a political score (political vendetta) before granting them freedom.

HISTORICAL EVOLUTION OF KIDNAPPING

The phenomenon of kidnapping in its earliest manifestation took the form of child abduction for ransom. Okoli and Agada (2014) maintained that the practice of kidnapping dates back to the 17th Century in Britain where infants (kids) of wealthy families would be ‘napped’ (caught in the sleep) for ransom. However, Linus (2015) maintained that in 1678, the word kidnapping was first recorded to mean kidnappers who piled their trade to secure laborers for plantations in colonies in North America. He further posits that kidnapping is a crime of unlawful, forceful seizure and detention of a person or persons against his/her will or their wish, in anticipation of payment of ransom or to settle some scores of dis-agreements.

Furthermore, Ottuh and Aitufe (2014), highlighted that the crime of kidnapping had been carefully taken into cognizance by ancient Rome as early as (AD 315), Emperor Constantine was so alarmed by the incident that he promulgated ‘death’ penalty as a punishment for such a crime. Also, Schuller (1985) opined that King Richard I of England was held hostage for years by the Arch Duke of Australia in the Twelfth century. In 1931, Ottuh and Aitufe (2014) noted that the upsurge in kidnapping in the USA led the Senate and House of Representatives to introduce Federal Legislation on Kidnapping. In Columbia, kidnapping has been viewed as a cottage industry, Thom and Blessing (2010), posited that the kidnappings in Columbia often cross over into Venezuela and Ecuador. Over the past two decades, the crime of kidnapping has persistently risen in most African countries, partially in Nigeria and South Africa, Thom & Blessing, (2010)

KIDNAPPING IN NIGERIA

The crime of kidnapping has assumed a new trend and has almost **become** a daily phenomenon in recent times. During the colonial period, kidnapping was vicious in the form of slavery in the 18th and 19th centuries as noted by Kelechi (2011). He posited that modern-day kidnapping in Nigeria started in the Niger Delta as a means of projecting their aggression and frustration towards the environmental hazards and effects of oil spillage in the area. Furthermore, (Onyejebu 2018, Akpan 2010, Kelechi 2011) pointed out that the deliberate acts of marginalization, deprivation, and endless accumulation of

natural resources and rents have been the driving force of the Niger Delta militants in the act of kidnapping. According to (John 2020, Onyejebu 2018, Okoli and Agada 2014, Ngwama 2014), the first well-known kidnapping after the colonial era started in 2006 when the militants of the Niger Delta took Total staff hostage to protest the inequality in the Region. The kidnapping started with the expatriates and later condescended to men of God, their children, politicians, religious leaders, lecturers, and students, and as it is today, everyone in Nigeria in one way or another is under threat of being kidnapped.

Reuters (2009) in Ngwama (2014) reported that in 2008, a total number of 512 kidnapping cases were reported in Nigeria. Ngwama (2014) noted that most of the kidnapping occurred in the Southeast and Niger Delta regions, which contains most of Nigeria's biggest oil well and gas plant. However, he pointed out that the hostages were released after payment of ransom and they were not harmed. Okoli and Agada (2014) noted that kidnapping has been used for different purposes ranging from political vendetta, rituals, and ransom amongst others. Furthermore, they posited that in the southeastern state, there was a decrease in armed robbery and other social vices with a persistent increase in kidnapping apparently because the majority of the perpetrators have taken to kidnapping. Kidnapping has increased in intensity and is perpetrated nationwide. The figures keep increasing each day, hence the need for concerted effort.

CAUSES OF KIDNAPPING

1. Abject Poverty

The effects of poverty on the livelihood of individuals have been a serious discourse in the academic world. John (2020) postulated that one of the main causes of kidnapping in Nigeria is poverty. He buttressed that poverty encompasses not only deprivation of material possessions but **also**, other deprivations like unemployment, ill-health, lack of education, powerlessness, and social exclusion amongst others. However, Yusuf and Abdullahi (2020), believe the reason why people indulge in kidnapping is to “exit from the track of poverty to riches”. They added that the ransom paid for kidnapping makes the perpetrator rich, compared to their miserable poverty state. The high rate of poverty in Nigeria has really widened the class disparity between the rich and the poor, hence the consistent increase in kidnapping to breach the gap and live a flamboyant life. In addition, kidnapping helps reduce poverty and meets family needs. Bello and Jamilu (2017) posited that economic deprivation and a sense of desperation have sowed the seed of desperation in communities and

kidnapping is the alternative. Kidnapping has been a source of income for the perpetrators. They use the ransom to meet their family needs, live a flamboyant life and join the affluents in the society. Poverty has been the primary reason many engage in heinous crime which is ravaging the nation and thereby affecting security. It is disheartening that Nigeria as a giant of Africa with natural mineral endowment and a large expanse of fertile land for agriculture has a high number of poor people who can barely afford two square meals a day and this has motivated them to commit so many crimes which kidnapping is one of them.

2. Unemployment

The persistent increase in the high rate of unemployment has been attributed to the cause of kidnapping in Nigeria, especially Youth Unemployment. Inyang (2009) has described Youth Unemployment as the driving factor encouraging kidnapping just like the maxim **says**, “an idle mind is the devil’s workshop”. Bello and Jamilu (2017) argued further that unemployment among youths and adolescents plays a key role in the consistent increase in kidnapping. Abdulkabir (2017) pointed out that most of the kidnappers convicted confessed that they were unemployed graduates looking for a means of survival. Furthermore, he opined that many youths have erred in joining criminal gangs because of unemployment and the search for jobs to earn a living. Ngwama (2014) added that if the level of Unemployment in Nigeria is not checkmated, soon the entire nation may have to be ransomed at one time or another. He further added that the kidnappers who had no livelihood believe they should take their destinies in their hands and collect whatever they could, at their disposal, in the face of continuous embezzling, stealing, and political crisis in the country.

Inyang (2009) reiterated that the proliferation of arms and ammunition as a result of godfatherism /patronage of those who were dumped after each election, may likely increase the spate of or encourage, kidnapping. The youths who were used and dumped by politicians after securing their winning ticket in the election are vulnerable to so many social vices and crimes, and most of them have picked up their arms and engaged in kidnapping, especially, the politicians. The unemployment index in Nigeria is increasing each year, with the tertiary institutions turning out graduates each year without corresponding companies, organizations, and institutions to gainfully employ them. Many get frustrated after fruitless years of searching for jobs and could engage in different crimes to sustain livelihood. The government is not doing its part as most companies that would have employed the youths are moribund because of bad management. Nigeria has a strong workforce waiting to be

gainfully employed which majority are the youths who are the number one perpetrators of kidnapping. They are easily manipulated as a result of frustration and unemployment and engage in different heinous crimes to make both ends meet.

3. Corruption & Political Leaders

The high rate of corruption in Nigeria's polity has been attributed as one of the causes of kidnapping in Nigeria. Yusuf and Abdullahi (2020) recounted that the advent of oil in the 1970s ignited heinous crimes in Nigeria, especially in the area of political office holders who were seen spending states resources frivolously, and the excluded minority in the area took kidnapping as an alternative. Bello and Jamilu (2017) emphasized that kidnapping evolved as a result of corruption in politics, where kidnapping was used to further the political aim of a particular group or movement. In this case, ransoms are usually paid to fund their movement. Ene (2017) posited that government officials especially top management level loot and spend recklessly government resources which encourages some of the perpetrators of these heinous crimes to engage in it as a way of showing their dissatisfaction and also earning a living. Ogabido (2009) reiterated that social injustice, inequality, unfair distribution of resources, and neglect of the host communities are some of the militating factors of kidnapping. He blamed the federal government for lack of equity and fairness in governance as well as lack of responsible leadership”.

The high rate of corruption witnessed in the last two decades is alarming, especially since political officeholders embezzle money meant for the construction of roads, water, hospitals, etc. with impunity and justice has not been brought to bear on them, as many evade the criminal justice and are in control of the judiciary. It is this persistent report on abuse of power and continuous embezzlement of government funds while the poor masses suffer that have triggered the persistent rise in kidnapping in Nigeria. In the opinion of Yusuf and Abdullahi (2020), attributed the rise in kidnappings to some politicians who kidnap for ritual purposes and political assassination to attain an enviable height in the nation's politics. They further opined that at each election children, imbeciles, and mentally deranged people are usually kidnapped for ritual purposes by some politicians and officeholders to maintain their position or climb higher on the ladder.

Okafor (2005) noted that the sum of 500 billion dollars has been stolen in the country through corruption from the sales of oil in the last 50 years which would have been used to improve the

economy, and as a result provide jobs for the youths. Corruption in Nigeria has almost become a household name. The embezzlement by those in authority has motivated the masses to take law into their hand. No wonder the majority of the kidnapped victims are those of high status in society. Corruption is so pronounced that the roads are in a deplorable state, hospitals are not equipped, epileptic power supply amongst others, yet huge amounts of money have been voted to take care of all these issues in the nation. This continuous abuse of offices has made many engage in the crime of kidnapping to get their fair share of the national cake.

4. Lack of Societal Value/ Moral Decadence

The culture of love for human lives, friendliness, hard work, and receptiveness to foreigners has been mortgaged in exchange for Western orientation (Ngwama, 2014). In a similar vein, Onovo (2009) correlated the persistent increase in crimes in Nigeria as a result of the celebration of fraudsters by leaders. He reiterated that the increase in crimes in the Southeast and South-South is caused by the quest for materialism and loss of societal values, people are ready to go the extra length to get wealth or material possessions at all cost, irrespective of whose horse is gored. Inyang (2009) posited that in Nigeria, nobody cares to question how one makes his/her wealth. He noted that anyone can show up with expensive vehicles and no one dares to question the sudden change in status/wealth. Onovo (2009) frowns at the appointment of indicted individuals as heads of various government agencies and parastatals.

The above has a negative effect on the youths and poor masses who watch with eagerness and see how the government treasury is looted with impunity and political holders amassing wealth without fear of being arrested, the youths in turn also take law into their hands, hence kidnapping. Umez (2000), attributes the value system in Nigeria as causes of kidnapping. He further stated that Nigeria glorifies and endorses illegal and corrupt means of income as sufficient and necessary means of earning a living which in turn has reshaped most Nigerian's integrity, especially the youths. No wonder the increase in cybercrime, kidnapping, and trafficking amongst others in society. Moral decadence has worsened in recent times giving room to different crimes in society. Those who perpetrate the cybercrime known as “YAHOO” are now celebrating their resourcefulness by obtaining money by false pretence and kidnapping is carried out in broad daylight. Other causes of kidnapping are; influence of hard drugs,

lack of capital punishment by the government, poor Security Infrastructure and bad governance as a result of leadership failure.

EFFECTS OF KIDNAPPING

The devastating effect of kidnapping on human society and the nation at large is enormous. The cankerworm seems to triumph despite concerted efforts by the security operatives to nip it in the bud. According to Dave et al. (2019), they pointed out that the perpetrators of kidnapping may have psychological challenges, for example, non-conformity with social orders like theft, violence, and aggression amongst others. Moreso, they posited that victims may experience depression, panic, suicidal ideations, and fear amongst others. The effect that kidnapping has on victims and society has called for concerted efforts to curtail and control the epidemics.

Effects/ Implication on Victims

The negative effects/implications of kidnapping on victims are devastating. Odoma and Akor (2019) averred that kidnapping affects not only the psychology of the direct victims and their families but also cuts across the economic investment by spreading fear which hinders economic productivity. The use of fear threatens the productive sector of the economy and it impacts negatively on the society. Bello and Jamilu (2017) added that the loss of contact has a traumatic effect on the parents of the victims and the victim. Again, they posited that victims may suffer from sexual abuse, especially the girl child, and could lead to the contraction of several deadly diseases. In addition, the victim's property may be disposed of to raise money for the ransom. Freeman (2006) noted that victims may suffer violence or torture from their perpetrators in the course of the abduction. Many victims have lost their lives as well as their livelihoods while the negotiation of ransom is ongoing. Sometimes, kidnappers end up battering and taking the lives of their victims.

It is worthy to note that while in the custody of the perpetrators, the environments are usually hostile and victims suffer from hunger due to lack of food and malnutrition. The aftermath effect of being kidnapped can weigh so much on the victims and relatives, according to Odoma and Akor (2019). They highlighted that victims suffer some psychological effects. There are occasions when victims have been asked to denounce their faith or face death in a (religious kidnapping). In another situation,

victims may be forced to sign documents or assent to an agreement for them to live. No matter the kind of kidnapping, they all possess a great effect and implication for the life, health, and security of victims. In some circumstances, victims' vital organs are been mutilated and harvested, and some are held in servitude, forced marriage, and labor. These negative effects affect and shape the behavior of victims and could lead to health and cognitive disorders.

Effects/ Implications on the economy

The economic effects of kidnapping could be direct or indirect. The direct cost could be in the form of money paid for ransom, or other economic property lost to the kidnappers, Ene (2018). Victims' relatives pay ransom to secure the release of their loved ones. This ransom could involve lending money, sales of valuable property, and financial savings. The indirect cost could be finance lost to secure or acquire security for preventive measures. At the national level, kidnapping could result in excess budget/ expenditure on security, Ene (2018). The implications are also witnessed in the area of manpower that produces goods and services for consumption and exports. This can be visible in the closure of some companies/establishments most of which are oil and gas companies as a result of incessant kidnapping, Dave et al. (2019).

Moreover, the persistent increase in kidnapping has deterred the industrialization of the nation and also rendered many jobless. This in turn has hindered foreign investments, and development in key sectors of the economy and has dented the image of the nation, (Ekpe 2019, Ene 2018, Inyang and Ibrahim, 2013). In addition, Ene et al. (2019) averred that the menace of kidnapping could hinder the capital and investment that comes as a result of foreign aid for natural development. Inyang and Abraham (2013) posited that the effects are manifest in the losses that the country experiences when an expatriate is kidnapped oil companies are attacked and the companies are shut down as a result of fear, which in turn reduces the national revenues generated. Bello and Jamilu (2017) posited that about five hundred million dollars [US\$500,000,000] are spent annually for ransom globally. Ngwama (2014) added that kidnapping is threatening the foundation of the Nigerian Economy and if not checkmated could lead the nation into recession. Yusuf and Abdullahi (2020) submitted that the Nation spent about (₦109.8 billion) for security in the year 2019, and this money could have been diverted to economic growth. Also, the advent of kidnapping in Nigeria has made many professionals leave the country as a result of being kidnapped. These professionals with relevant skills in different works of life leave the nation in search of a secure and greener pasture.

Psychological effects/ Implications

Kidnapping has lots of devastating effect on the victim and affect the psychology of the victim (Yusuf and Abdul 2020, Odoma and Akor 2019, Ene 2018, Bello and Jamilu (2017). In addition, Soyombo (2016) pointed out that kidnapping barricades people's social life by restricting their movement. Yusuf and Abdullahi (2020) observed that kidnapping results in post-traumatic stress disorder because of the horrifying scenes of the acts. Movement in Nigeria has been restricted solely because of the persistent increase in kidnapping especially on some roads. Wealthy and influential people have to travel with lots of escorts and night movement has become so risky. Yusuf and Abdullahi (2020) added that house/ company owners disguise themselves as taxi drivers and Okada man in a bid to move freely in society. Family members, and relatives of the victims suffer lots of abuse verbally and psychologically in order to get their loved ones free from the net of kidnappers. Sometimes, the kidnappers threaten to kill the victim or abuse them physically or mentally. The thought of a price tag on the head of the victim affects the victim and the family members.

Social Implication/Effect of Kidnapping

The menace of kidnapping affects the social life of many people. The continuous use of curfew to curb as the menace affects the social life of the inhabitants, more so, there is a heightened level of mistrust according to Inyang and Abraham (2013), very few people in the society extend their African hospitality to strangers as a result of growing awareness of the dangers of talking or sharing information with strangers, who could be kidnappers. Also, kidnapping has restricted movement or visitation as well as limited attendance to important ceremonies like marriage, funerals, birthdays, etc. (Dave et al. 2019). There is also a continuous increase in the demand for escorts which has reduced the capacity and effectiveness of the security agencies to curtail the menace.

Political appointees, affluent individuals, and business tycoons amongst others demand escort from the security agencies in their daily movement. This has reduced the security agencies' workforce and also undermined their capability of securing the lives and property of the citizens. Dave et al. (2019) posited that many have lost their lives, belongings, properties, etc. as a result of the menace of kidnapping. They portend that where the breadwinner of the family is affected, it could create a serious dangerous gap in the family and be difficult to fill in the long run. Ngwama (2014) posited that kidnapping could lead to a threat to industrial harmony and destabilization of the labor market which

in the long run falls back on the society, and could manifest in unemployment, closure of factories / companies producing goods and services, migration or movement of people to areas less prone to insecurity etc.

CONCEPTUALISING NATIONAL SECURITY

Security generally is a crosscutting and multi-dimensional concept which has, over the last century, been the subject of great debate. The concept of security has undergone a transition from traditional conceptualization to a non-traditional meaning, CSS (241). Traditionally, security management was the absolute responsibility of the state especially if we consider the scholarly view(s) of some political philosophers like Thomas Hobbes (1962) who posited that the essence of a state is to “guarantee the security of lives and property and ensure law and order through its political sovereignty and monopoly of violence”. After the end of the Cold War and owing to globalization, security management has taken a new dimension. The external threat to security resulting from international hostilities and aggression that characterized the Cold War era was replaced with non-traditional security threats like information warfare, drug trafficking, nuclear pollution, disease epidemics like HIV-AIDS, corruption, human trafficking, (internal) insurgency, among others, CSS (241).

However, according to the White House, security is seen as “an all-encompassing condition in which Individual citizens live in freedom, peace and Safety; participate fully in the process of governance; Enjoy the protection of fundamental rights; have Access to resources and the necessities of life; And inhabit an environment which is not detrimental to their health and wellbeing” (South Africa White Paper on Defence, 1996). According to Igbuzor (2011), security is “the situation that exists as a result of the establishment of measures for the protection of persons, information and property against hostile persons, influences and actions., it is the existence of conditions within which people in a society can go about their normal daily activities without any threats to their lives or property. It demands safety from chronic threats and protection from harmful disruption” Security may also be defined as protection against something that might happen in the future or as the activities involved in protecting a country, a building, or persons against threats danger, etc., (Wehmeier and Ashby, 2002).

In the opinion of Eme (2011), security can be seen as the “stability and continuity of livelihood, predictability of daily life, protection from crime and freedom from psychological harm. Therefore, security can be described and summarized as the protection against all forms of harm (whether

physical, economic, or psychological). The different submission of scholars on security connotes that security is all about freedom from fear, turmoil, danger, hostility, violence, war, and any other event that can cause uneasiness for humans and nations. Imobighe (2002) buttressed the importance of security to humans and nations when he posited that “without security, individuals within a state will find it difficult to engage in productive activities”. Similarly, Abraham (2020) submitted that without security “the state is bound to experience great difficulty in harnessing its human and material resources towards meaningful development and the promotion of the general well-being of the people”. From the foregoing, it suffices that security is about the protection of lives and property, danger from threat (including natural disasters, and man-made hazards), and anything that could threaten the peace and security of the citizen. Some security approaches can be explained;

Idealism: The approach was well known in the 1920s, the approach believes in a non-coercive or non-violent process, because violence would only give birth to further violence. This school of thought believed that security is best managed if government at all levels (from local to national) could ensure that a security system ‘based on the development of civic culture on international agreements and treaties could stress “depolarization, demilitarization, transcendence of enemy imaging, and solidarity” (Kasali, 2003). It further portends that democratic governance is the ultimate mechanism for effective security management, hence the advocacy of democracy and good governance. However, the emergence and catastrophes that World War II brought have undermined the importance and relevance of this approach in the management of security both national and international particularly as it concerned the issues of democratic order, CSS (241). In addition, experiences and issues have highlighted that democracy may not guarantee peace and security and some democracies can carry out offensives capable of jeopardizing national and international (security) as seen in Hiroshima, Nagasaki, and other places which undermine national security.

Realism approach to security emerged as a result of the failure of the idealism which could not prevent the outbreak of World War II. This school of thought accepts and emphasizes coercion and deterrence to maintain internal and external security. Moreso, they believed it was only through the use of force or violence (coercion) that peace can be achieved and security maintained. CSS (241) submits that this approach achieves effective management of security through the balance of power and multi-deterrence mechanisms. It further buttressed that the Realist prioritizes self-interest agenda, by

evaluating and analyzing the available policy options and ultimately maximizes those options which meet their security objectives. However, there has been a continuous production and stockpiling of weapons (including weapons of mass destruction) by different nations to manage national security and resist all security threats, CSS (241).

The aftermath effect of the foregoing is obvious in developing nations like Africa, which has diverted surplus money meant for development into buying weapons for security and more spending to keep to the task. CSS (241) opined that this has created more challenges and deepening political crises, military coups, and countercoups, inter-ethnic violence, and religious bestiality among others. The obvious fact is that instead of acquiring military wares for external aggression or threats, these weapons have now been used for internal purpose against their citizens for a variety of reasons which ranges from tenure elongation, racial discrimination, ethnic rivalry, religious chauvinism, etc.

Pluralism approach emerged owing to the failure of Realism. It emerged in the 1960s. This approach had a divergent view from the self-centered interest, balance of power of realism which has failed and exposed the state to armament. Pluralism admonishes states to jettison any of their self-interest policies that are considered to be immoral or capable of undermining international security to mutual benefits and harmonious co-existence of nations.

The Human security is a new and broadened approach in security studies, it exposes the effect of environment, social interaction and poverty, and on how they contribute to conflict and affect the security of lives and property, Abraham (2020). The key message of this approach is that human security deprivations can undermine peace in the society and nation, hence the advocacy on human security which entails all that threaten the peace and tranquility of the society. Threat to society in the form of deadly disease outbreak like Coronavirus, Ebola, AIDS, and global warming has persistently increased as cankerworm ready to destroy the human race, and the volcanic nationalism that greeted post-cold War era has become a major source of state collapse, (CSS 241).

It is based on the aforementioned that gave room in the 1990s, to redefine security and seek an approach to security suitable to guarantee effective security management, which differs from the formal approaches that have failed to live up to expectations. CSS (241). The human security approach

advocates for a paradigm shift from the state-centered response to security to people in the society who make up the state to define their security.

The importance of this approach was popularized and nurtured for addressing security threats facing people which was contained in the 1994 UNDP Human Development Report (12). Given this, security has been redefined to mean an all-encompassing condition in which individual citizens live in freedom, peace, which and safety; to participate fully in the process of governance; enjoy the protection of fundamental rights; have access to resources and the necessities of life; and inhabit an environment which is not detrimental to their health and well-being” (South African Department of Defence, 1996) and other countries have borrowed a leaf from the UNDP report on the need for dynamic human security.

The UNDP developed a new working definition of security where it outlined human security to be “a child who did not die, a disease that does not spread, a job that was not cut, an ethnic tension that did not explode in violence, a dissident who was not silenced”. Therefore, suffice it to say that human security denotes the degree to which the welfare of individuals in society is protected and promoted. The persistent increase insecurity that has threatened human survival, existence, and life safety, or exposed humans to different uncertainties of disease and pestilence, or subjected vulnerable people to penury related to economic downturns demands that special attention be paid to the dangers of sudden deprivation.

The human security approach implores protection from the aforementioned dangers and the empowerment of people so that they can cope better in society. The previous approaches of coercion and deterrence which was the traditional security measure were incapable of meeting the 21st century demand on the security of lives and property of the citizen and also taking cognizance of other threat in the form of natural disaster, diseases, hunger, famine, global warming, desertification amongst others, hence the redefining of the term security as people-centered security to meet existing need in the society and thereby reducing conflicts and factors which threaten the coexistence of man in the society. Many nations and policy-makers in several countries around the world have adopted this approach as the guiding principle of their security laws.

NATIONAL SECURITY

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National security has been viewed by different scholars in different ways, most of which emphasize the collective responsibility of the state. Position of Hartmann in Ebeh (2015) defined national security as “the total of the vital national interest of the state, and because a vital national interest is one of which a nation is willing to resort to force or war either immediately or ultimately, concept of national security will vary from state to state in direct proportion to their willingness to risk either conflict or war at any given time.” However, Brennan in Ebeh (2015) opined that national security is “the protection of national survival” Accordingly to Ehi (2009), “national security must include the capacity to provide the citizens with social, economic and political conditions conducive to happiness and relative prosperity. Thus, tranquility and well-being of a society are necessary components of national security”.

However, Ray in Ebeh (2015) lent credence to it by portraying national security to be understood in terms of the desire and capacity for self-defense, hence the ability of the state to maintain its internal and external threats. In the opinion of Omotola (2006), national security is “the freedom from danger or absence of threats to the multidimensional elements that may affect the nation’s ability to protect and develop itself, promote its cherished values and national interests, as much as promote and boost the well-being of its people”. More so, Peterside (2018) added that national security is “the freedom from actual and potential threats to national life that may arise as a result of human action or inactions, or from a disaster such as a flood, earthquake, famine, drought, disease and other natural calamitous events resulting in deaths, human suffering, and material damage”.

Asad (2007) submitted “that national security cannot be narrowed down to exclusively military term. Similarly, Onuoha (2017) posits that national security is “the capacity of a state to promote the pursuit and realization of the fundamental needs and vital interests of man and society and to protect them from threats which may be economic, social, environmental, political, military or epidemiologic in nature”. However, Eme and Onyishi (2014) took a divergent view in the Nigerian setting. They highlighted that national security defined in terms of national survival in Nigeria is an illusion. It is an “illusion because it is an erroneous perception of the African reality”. They posited that national security in Africa especially Nigeria is used by the “milling elite as a fine transparent concept for deluding the populace into thinking that government policies in this regard represent actions designed actually to protect them from hunger, disease, injustice, and violation of human dignity and life”. In

furtherance to their view, ‘national security gave rise to two dangerous doctrines of illusionism and militarism which is self-defeating. They argued, that national security in Nigeria refers to a “guarantee of peace and stability determined by ethno-religious/communal harmony; peaceful coexistence; food security; sustainable socioeconomic development; and democratic development.

Also, accounting for the security of the nation is strengthening the rule of law; creating a democratic political culture; nurturing civility, promoting good governance, transparency and structural reforms amenable to democratization. However, the aforementioned are a mere mirage in Nigeria, as security is only words in the letter not in the practice of the nation. It is therefore misleading to equate national security with the security of the state because the Nigerian state is a capitalist state that uses the instrument for the preservation of socio-economic formation, which protects the interests of a privileged class of people, hence the poor masses suffer. National security is a welcome development if practised to the latter. The security of the citizen remains paramount as the sole responsibility of the state, to ensure citizens do not suffer harm from external and internal threats and other social threats like hunger, famine, unemployment, and disease outbreak amongst others. The submission of the UNDP that security involves the people, not the state-centered military hardware has been brought to bear and remains a sine qua non for citizens' wellbeing.

KIDNAPPING AND NATIONAL SECURITY IN NIGERIA

The persistent effects of kidnapping have grossly affected national security in Nigeria. Peterside (2018), submitted that national security is “the freedom from actual and potential threats to national life that may arise as a result of human action or inactions, or from a disaster such as a flood, earthquake, famine, drought, disease and other natural calamitous events resulting in deaths, human suffering, and material damage”. However, the adverse effect of kidnapping has defied the efficacy of the state to guarantee the safety and security of the lives of her citizens. The nation has witnessed low patronage in foreign exchange and investment as a result of kidnapping which is threatening the basic foundation of the nation. Odoma and Akor (2019) averred that kidnapping affects not only the psychology of the direct victims and their families but also cuts across the economic investment by spreading fear which hinders economic productivity.

Fear threatens the productive sector of the economy and it impacts negatively on the society. In addition, the victim’s property may be disposed to raise money for the ransom. In addition, Ene et al.

(2019) buttressed that the menace of kidnapping could hinder the capital investment that comes as a result of foreign aid for national development. Inyang and Abraham (2013) posited that the effects are manifest in the losses that the country experiences when an expatriate is kidnapped oil companies are attacked and the companies are shut down as a result of fear, which in turn reduces the national revenues generated. Ngwama (2014) added that kidnapping is threatening the foundation of the Nigerian Economy and if not checkmated could lead the nation into recession. There is a heightened level of mistrust according to Inyang and Abraham (2013) who posited that very few people in the society extend their African hospitality to strangers as a result of growing awareness of the dangers of talking/sharing information with strangers, who could be kidnappers.

Also, kidnapping has restricted movement/visitation as well as limited attendance to important ceremonies like marriage, funerals, birthdays, etc. (Dave et al, 2019). Ngwama (2014) posited that kidnapping could lead to a threat to industrial harmony and destabilization of the labour market which the long run falls back on the society, which could manifest in unemployment, closure of factories/companies producing goods and services, migration/movement of people to areas less prone to insecurity. It is evident in the commercial cities of Aba, Bauchi, and Kano amongst others which is characterized by lawlessness, prompting residents to flee the town in droves, while schools, banks, markets, and business premises have been shut down. The main targets of these criminals are usually members of the upper and middle classes, including politicians and their children, business tycoons, lecturers, and professionals amongst others who could afford the ransom demanded of the criminals.

These aforementioned would have helped to grow the economy of the nation and project the nation, but the security threat of the kidnappers has deterred them from engaging and investing in the nation. Ezugwu (2017) noted that because of the ravaging heinous crime of kidnapping for ransom, some state governors called for stricter penalties or laws that would put a stop to kidnapping. The kidnapping has crippled the economic activities, caused the closure of many Multi-National Companies, hindered foreign investment, increased insecurity in the nation, and accounted for so many other social vices which rampage the nation and this reverberates in increased spending on security, economic hardship, insecurity, restriction of movement, amongst others. Kidnapping is a security threat that has impacted negatively on the nation and persists amidst concerted efforts to nip it in the bud. The kidnapping of school students, Abayi, Dapchi, and Chibok amongst others also opened the eyes of the public on the danger and security threat inherent in kidnapping, and the extent the criminal could perpetrate their

wickedness and this has led to many parents sending their children to a distance school or even outside the nation.

Kidnapping has also dented the image of the nation in recent times and this has resulted in the nation being marked as a black spot by the Western world. The inadequacy of law enforcement agents to control kidnapping and maintain security has been a major concern for all and sundry. Kidnapping has undermined the power or capacity of the state to protect its citizens. Onuoha (2017) posits that national security is “the capacity of a state to promote the pursuit and realization of the fundamental needs and vital interests of man and society, and to protect them from threats which may be economic, social, environmental, political, military or epidemiologic in nature”. Based on the submission above, the prevalence of kidnapping in the nation has not only hindered the populace from pursuing and realizing fundamental needs but has also become a threat to the lives, economic, social, and otherwise of the members of the society. Kidnapping has undermined security and seems to have aborted the efforts law enforcement, agencies.

THE WAY FORWARD

It is a general norm that the identification of a problem in a research work helps to proffer a solution to the problem. The scourge and epidemics of kidnapping that have threatened national security emanate from causal factors; poverty, unemployment, get-rich syndrome, and greed amongst others. These factors have necessitated the persistent increase in the crime of kidnapping and have impacted negatively, security hence the security of lives and property which is the sole responsibility of the state has been undermined. The rippling effects are visible in all of the sectors of the economy. The need to provide job opportunities, capital investments, revitalization of abandoned firms or industry, and good governance amongst others are sine qua non for the eradication of kidnapping which affects security adversely. Moreso, the security agencies are to be reformed, rebranded, retrained, equipped, and properly funded to wage the war against kidnapping. Also, the Nigerian State should review and vigorously implement laws and policies relevant to the criminalization of kidnapping, this will act as deterrence to the kidnappers.

Political leaders and god-fathers using youths to achieve political aims and cause mayhem in society should be arrested and prosecuted. The construction of roads, provision of social amenities, rural development, and partnership with foreign companies to build industries should be the government

watchwords. The fight against corruption in Nigeria should be intensified and should cut across all the sectors of the nation. Rule of law should prevail, an egalitarian society free from nepotism and favoritism, and security should not be limited to the office holders but to everyone in the society.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Kidnapping has adversely impacted on the national security. Security therefore is a necessary element for peace and national development in Nigeria. The persistent increase in kidnapping in Nigeria has masterminded the peace, security and development. Kidnapping which has deterred foreign investors, crippled most of the firms, caused loss of lives and property seem to triumph unabated, hence the need to curtail the ugly situation in time. This would reduce kidnapping and the security threat that it breeds. Unfortunately, due to the insecurity in the nation as a result of kidnapping which is embedded in poverty, greed, political interference, and moral decadence amongst others, the security and development of the nation have been threatened and is under siege. This has threatened and deterred foreign investment, affected the trade and even the educational institution amongst others. There is urgent need to contain and control kidnapping which affects national security in Nigeria.

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